

A three-lens architecture for circular economy education: Technical, Economic and Psychosocial

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Abstract

Circular Economy decision making requires integration of technical feasibility, economic viability and psychosocial acceptance, yet higher education courses often present these domains without forcing students to resolve cross lens tensions under real world constraints. This paper presents a Circular Economy teaching methodology developed and delivered at TH Köln, centred on a Three Lens Circular Economy Teaching Architecture grounded in systems thinking accounts of feedbacks, unintended consequences and trade-offs. The methodology was implemented through a designed fourteen week sequence that combined lectures with embedded micro interventions and three in class exercises, with analysis based on group level artefacts and instructor notes from Exercise 1, Exercise 2 and Exercise 3. The analysed outputs show that the exercises elicit lens specific reasoning and recurring cross lens tensions, including cases where technically feasible options become fragile under business model constraints or adoption limits, and that later exercises demanded more integration lenses and across stakeholders than earlier exercises. The results support the architecture as a transferable decision scaffold that makes integration an explicit performance through standardised lens questions, structured group artefacts and plenary synthesis, while the evidence base remains qualitative and does not support strong claims about individual learning gains or causal effects of specific sessions.

Keywords: Circular Economy education; Decision competence; Systems thinking; Economic viability; Psychosocial acceptance; Problem based learning

1. Introduction

The circular economy has gained worldwide relevance as a strategy to reduce environmental pressures while strengthening resource security and economic resilience through value retention in products and materials (De Sa and Korinek, 2021). Policy frameworks increasingly link circularity to reduced dependence on imported critical raw materials, positioning value retention pathways e.g. reuse, repair, refurbish, re-manufacture, recycle etc as levers for strategic autonomy and supply security (EC, 2020; Council of the European Union, 2024).

Circular economy transitions require decisions that cut across technology, markets and stakeholder acceptance, and are often shaped by competing values and constraints. Such transitions are frequently characterised by wicked problems where multiple stakeholders, irreducible complexity and contested priorities limit the possibility of a single best answer (Rittel and Webber, 1973). Barriers to circular economy implementation have been grouped into social and cultural, institutional and regulatory, economic and market and technological dimensions (de Jesus and Mendonça, 2018; Paletta et al., 2019; Grafström and Aasma, 2021). Within the European Union, social and cultural barriers have been identified as particularly influential, reflecting mindsets, mental models, sensitivity and awareness that shape adoption and collaboration (Kirchherr et al., 2018; Schultz and Reinhardt, 2022). Prominent barriers include limited stakeholder awareness and demand, organisational reservation or company culture, limited willingness for collaboration, inadequate knowledge of circular economy principles and practices and the absence of operational approaches, including viable business models and product design strategies for implementation (Mangla et al., 2018; Bonsu, 2020; Hina et al., 2022). These barriers rarely operate in isolation and often surface as trade-offs between technical feasibility, economic incentives and psychosocial acceptance, producing conflicting yet defensible conclusions about the same circular strategy.

Such cross domain trade-offs can be illustrated through a circular strategy for clothing that aims to retain value through durability, repair services and resale. A technical analysis can support longer lifetimes through material choices, design for repair and quality standards, yet an economic analysis can show margin pressure where revenues depend on high turnover unless the business model shifts to services, take back or resale value capture. A psychosocial analysis can then reveal adoption limits driven by fast fashion norms, hygiene perceptions and cultural preferences even when functional quality is comparable. The same circular strategy can therefore appear feasible, unprofitable or socially resisted depending on the lens, so decisions require explicit integration of constraints across lenses.

Education is repeatedly highlighted as essential for change in knowledge, values, behaviours and lifestyles in sustainability and circular economy contexts (Pandey and Vedak, 2010), yet the adoption of educational strategies on these themes remains limited (Wiek et al., 2014; Keramitsoglou et al., 2023). Teaching circular economy is challenging because the concept is contested and defined in multiple ways, and its meaning is negotiated in practice among diverse actors rather than being fixed (Rödl et al., 2022). Furthermore, multi disciplinary and systems thinking approaches can be difficult to convey to students with diverse academic backgrounds, creating a steep learning curve and risking uneven participation (Wiek et al., 2014). In related sustainability education literature, Lim et al. (2015) argue that higher education benefits from pedagogical strategies that shift from transmissive to discovery learning, from teacher centred to student centred approaches and from theoretical to practice oriented learning. Therefore, problem based learning (PBL) has been widely applied to stimulate learning motivation, problem solving and research skills through collaborative student centred work and is commonly used in circular economy and adjacent sustainability contexts (Wiek et al., 2014; Chang et al., 2018; Randles et al., 2022).

There is no defined best teaching style for circular economy teaching and many courses add “circularity and/or sustainability content” to engineering and business curricula without structural integration (Sabri, 2025). In addition, some courses that integrate circularity more explicitly still juxtapose technical, economic and social considerations without requiring students to integrate them into a justified decision under real world constraints (Pargmann and Berding, 2025). However,

systems thinking frame offers a good way to define what circular economy competence entails and why it cannot be reduced to a collection of tools. In classic systems thinking accounts, complex systems display nonlinear behaviour, feedback loops and unintended consequences, and interventions often create trade-offs rather than unambiguous improvements (Senge, 1990; Sterman, 2002; Meadows, 2008). For circular economy decisions, this implies an integration requirement across interacting systems: a technical system that concerns material and energy flows across defined system boundaries, an economic system that concerns incentives, costs, benefits and business models and a psychosocial system that concerns acceptance, legitimacy, perceived fairness and predictable biases in judgement.

This paper presents a Circular Economy teaching methodology developed and delivered at TH Köln, grounded in systems thinking accounts that emphasise feedbacks, unintended consequences and trade-offs, centred on a Three Lens Circular Economy Teaching Architecture, with qualitative evidence of student decision competence drawn from group level course artefacts produced in three embedded exercises.

2. Pedagogical Innovation - Three-Lens Circular Economy Teaching Architecture

Figure 1 summarises the Three Lens Circular Economy Teaching Architecture. The architecture frames Circular Economy education as integrated decision making across interacting constraints rather than separate disciplinary blocks. Proposals that appear circular within one lens can fail in practice when constraints from another lens are made explicit, so the pedagogical aim is to develop decision competence under trade-offs by requiring students to analyse the same option through technology, economy and psychosocial acceptance and justify a decision.

The lenses are implemented through a standardised set of guiding questions applied across cases. The technology lens addresses technical feasibility, life cycle scope and system boundaries, prioritising inner loops before recycling. The economic lens makes explicit who pays, who benefits and who earns, examining externalities, incentives and business model fit. The psychosocial lens examines acceptance and legitimacy, including how framing, predictable biases and credibility checks shape adoption and evaluation. The overlap in Figure 1 represents options more likely to remain feasible, viable and acceptable when constraints are considered together.

Integration is operationalised through repeated application of the lenses to the same problem using scaffolded practice. Early activities use instructor guidance to model how lens specific analysis leads to a justified decision, while later activities shift responsibility to student led analysis and peer critique. The innovation lies not in naming three domains, but in specifying lens questions and integration prompts so that assessment focuses on justified decisions under stated boundaries, assumptions and uncertainties rather than recall, supporting transfer as a repeatable decision scaffold.

3. Methods

3.1 Course setting and participants

Figure 1: Three-Lens Circular Economy Teaching Architecture used in the course. The figure shows the technical lens, the economic lens and the psychosocial lens and their overlaps, distinguishing solutions that are feasible, financeable and acceptable, with the central overlap indicating a lasting circular solution.

The study was conducted in an elective Circular Economy course delivered in English at Technische Hochschule Köln, Campus Gummersbach. The course was open to undergraduate students across semesters and drew mainly informatics and engineering related bachelor programmes at the campus, including computer science, business informatics, media informatics, information technology management, industrial engineering with specialisations in electrical engineering, mechanical engineering and environmental engineering and mechanical engineering. The course was delivered in five iterative trials from winter semester 2023/24 to winter semester 2025/26, with enrolments of n = 24 (Trial 1), n = 11 (Trial 2), n = 10 (Trial 3), n = 8 (Trial 4) and n = 17 (Trial 5). Only data from Trials 4 and 5 were analysed in this paper, since the three in class exercises and two micro interventions were implemented consistently in these trials. Given the degree backgrounds, participants were expected to have prior experience with technical reasoning, some participants were expected to have prior exposure to economic decision making and none were expected to have prior formal education in psychosocial aspects of adoption and judgement. The research material comprised group artefacts produced during the exercises and instructor notes recorded during and immediately after each exercise session. No personal data such as names, grades or contact details were collected and the analysis uses only group level artefacts.

The main learning objective of this course was to enable students to make and justify circular economy decisions for real world cases using a Three-Lens Circular Economy Teaching Architecture covering technology, economy and psychosocial acceptance. Transversal to the learning objective, the course had four intended learning outcomes for the students: (1) demonstrate the ability to analyse a circular economy option by defining system boundaries and by stating key assumptions and uncertainties across the three lenses to support a defensible professional recommendation, (2) design and compare value retention options for products and services by applying design for R principles and circular business model logic to propose context appropriate redesign strategies, (3) compare circular options by applying life cycle assessment (LCA) conventions and boundary choices, including functional unit definition and scope decisions, to make trade-offs transparent under competing objectives, and (4) critically evaluate corporate circularity and sustainability claims and responsibility framings by applying evidence checks, indicator logic and framing analysis to identify potential greenwashing and reduce the risk of unsupported organisational decisions.

3.2 Course structure, content and sequencing

The course was designed as a fourteen week sequence that can be mapped to a typical semester structure, as summarised in Figure 2 as a timeline with sessions labelled by week and coded by format using icons. Table 2 documents the pedagogical intent, content focus, design element, methods characteristic and sequencing link for instructor designed sessions, including lectures with embedded micro interventions and the three in class exercises, while project clinics, student project work and final presentations are excluded. Section 4 analyses only artefacts and instructor notes recorded during Exercise 1, Exercise 2 and Exercise 3, with micro interventions treated as course context.

Figure 2: Course sequence overview and session formats across a designed fourteen week timeline. Each week is labelled by week number and coded by session format, providing transfer context for the analysed exercises.

Table 2: Course structure, content and sequencing for instructor designed teaching sessions in the designed fourteen week sequence. The table includes lectures with embedded micro interventions and the three in class exercises, while project clinics, student project work and final presentations are excluded. Analysed evidence in Section 4 is drawn only from artefacts and instructor notes recorded during Exercise 1, Exercise 2 and Exercise 3, with micro interventions treated as course context. #L: Lecture number corresponding to the week number.

#L*	Pedagogical intent	Content	Design element	Methods characteristic	Sequencing link
1	Establish a shared baseline for why linear economy systems fail and why Circular Economy decision making is required	Linear versus circular system logic and material flows; historical extraction and regional Ruhr vignette; impact categories associated with linear systems; course framing and assessment overview; positioning of wider environmental impacts as context rather than course aim.	Visual contrast between closed natural cycles and open industrial flows, supported by historical and regional vignettes.	Instructor guided conceptual framing with visual evidence and structured discussion.	Creates shared language for flows, losses and loops, supporting boundary setting and the Three-Lens Architecture in Exercise 1.
2	Establish a shared reference model of Circular Economy and the link to business value.	Circular Economy definition with technical and biological loops; value retention logic and inner loop priority; acquisition, reprocessing and remarketing as implementation steps; business value and incentives; assessment expectations.	One system diagram used as an anchor and revisited later.	Instructor guided walkthrough with guided questions and short discussion.	Provides shared vocabulary and a system map needed before lens based analysis and before feasibility, economic viability and acceptability reasoning.
3	Introduce the Three-Lens Architecture and use it in a first lens based exercise.	Three-Lens Architecture, lens questions and boundaries, forever product case, trade-offs across technology, economy and psychosocial factors.	Lens team format plus plenary synthesis that makes lens creep visible.	Small group work with short reporting rounds and instructor synthesis notes.	Establishes the lens logic used throughout and produces plenary synthesis notes and group level outputs from Exercise 1 that are analysed in Section 4.
5	Make cognitive biases and CO ₂ framing visible as decision risks in Circular Economy work.	CO ₂ framing, cognitive biases relevant to Circular Economy decisions, reflection prompts for claim checking.	Framing contrasts and a short bias checklist used in discussion.	Short embedded micro intervention with instructor facilitated reflection.	Introduces psychosocial decision risks that are referenced in later lens discussions, treated as course context in this paper.
6	Build capability to describe and compare circular design options.	Value retention routes and circular design principles; repair, reuse, remanufacture and recycle examples;	A value retention ladder and	Instructor guided explanation with guided discussion.	Provides the shared design vocabulary for value retention routes used in Exercise 2.

7	Practise applying all three lenses to a value retention route and make trade-offs explicit.	circular business model logic; typical constraints and enablers. Repair and reuse, remanufacture and recycle routes, lens based constraints and enablers, explicit trade off articulation.	contrasting case snapshots. One page group worksheet that forces lens coverage and justification.	Structured group work with instructor circulation and plenary synthesis.	Produces one group worksheet per route plus plenary synthesis notes that are analysed in Section 4.
8	Introduce biological loop concepts needed for food waste and organics cases.	Biological loop logic, anaerobic digestion and composting concepts, nutrient cycling, regional organics relevance.	Process schematics and simplified mass flow reasoning prompts.	Instructor guided conceptual walkthrough with short questions.	Introduces biological loop concepts referenced in Exercise 3.
9	Apply the Three-Lens Architecture to a biological loop case using structured lens worksheets.	Food waste case, lens specific problem framing, boundary choices, solutions and constraints per lens.	Lens specific worksheets plus a plenary synthesis that compares lens outputs.	Small group work and instructor led synthesis using captured notes.	Produces lens specific worksheets and plenary synthesis notes that are analysed in Section 4.
11	Introduce life cycle assessment boundary logic and surface justice constraints in comparative claims.	Life cycle assessment basics, functional unit and boundary setting, comparative limits, justice and distributional effects as decision constraints.	Boundary sketching prompts and discussion questions that reveal value choices.	Embedded micro intervention with instructor guided explanation and discussion.	Makes boundary choices and justice constraints explicit as decision considerations, treated as course context in this paper.
12	Make implementation barriers visible and connect Circular Economy options to maturity and investment constraints.	Technical barriers framed through 9 technology readiness levels (TRL) and an example progression case; social, economic and systemic barriers, including the valley of death and resource constraints.	TRL ladder and valley of death curve as the two anchor visuals, supported by one mapped example.	Instructor guided walkthrough with guided questions and short discussion.	Documents implementation constraints referenced in later course work, treated as course context in this paper.
13	Provide a structured template to describe business models for Circular Economy options and make incentive logic explicit.	Business model definition and Business Model Canvas (BMC), presented through the nine building blocks with illustrative examples across blocks.	BMC diagram used as the anchor, presented block by block with a short worked example.	Instructor guided walkthrough with guided questions and short application prompts.	Provides a shared template for project work and later economic viability discussions, treated as course context in this paper.

*Session numbering follows the designed sequence in Figure 2.

3.3. Embedded learning activities

Embedded learning activities comprised three in class exercises and two micro interventions delivered within instructor led sessions. Activities used structured prompts, small group discussion and plenary synthesis to make three lens reasoning visible and comparable. Analysed evidence reported in Section 4 is based only on group artefacts and instructor notes from Exercise 1, Exercise 2 and Exercise 3. Micro interventions, project clinics, student projects and final presentations are treated as course context and are not analysed in this paper.

Exercise 1 focused on durability and value retention using a shared forever product case. Students worked in three teams, one per lens, presented their conclusions and compared tensions in a facilitated plenary discussion. Artefacts comprised one team summary per lens and instructor notes capturing unique points and instances of lens creep.

Exercise 2. ocused on value retention routes for a common product, a smartphone. Students were assigned to three route groups, repair and reuse, remanufacture and recycle, and each group applied all three lenses to its assigned route using a structured one page worksheet. Groups presented their outputs and the class compared route specific trade-offs in plenary discussion, supported by instructor notes. Artefacts comprised one completed worksheet per group and instructor notes. The worksheet template and prompts are provided in the Supplementary Material.

Exercise 3. focused on the biological loop using a food waste case. Students were assigned to three lens teams, technical, economic and psychosocial, and each team generated stage specific proposals across farm to fork and identified the stakeholder expected to act. Teams completed lens specific worksheets, followed by a plenary synthesis that compared complementarities and conflicts across lenses. Artefacts comprised three worksheets per class and instructor notes from the plenary synthesis. The worksheet templates and prompts are provided in the Supplementary Material.

Micro intervention 1 and Micro intervention 2 used structured worksheets to support judgement about framing effects, boundary choices and impacts that sit outside a chosen assessment frame, without extending the analysed evidence base beyond the three exercises. Problem based learning projects ran in parallel, with students selecting either a linear to Circular Economy business transformation theme or a corporate Circular Economy and sustainability claim evaluation theme, supported through interim feedback milestones and final presentations, but their outputs are not analysed in this paper.

4. Results

4.1 Evidence of decision competence across lenses

Table 3 summarises analysed outputs from Exercise 1, Exercise 2 and Exercise 3 using the Three-Lens Circular Economy Teaching Architecture. In this paper, cross lens decision competence is treated as evidence of lens specific reasoning in group artefacts, including explicit scope choices and constraints where relevant and articulation of trade-offs between technical feasibility, economic viability and psychosocial acceptance. The results report what is visible in the analysed outputs rather than individual learning gains. Across the three exercises, indicators include groups stating lens specific arguments, making constraints explicit and linking feasibility, viability and acceptance rather than treating Circular Economy decisions as a single domain optimisation.

Table 3: Evidence of cross lens decision competence based on analysed group outputs from Exercise 1, Exercise 2 and Exercise 3. The table summarises lens specific reasoning observed in group artefacts and the cross lens tension summarised from plenary synthesis using group outputs and instructor notes.

Exercise	Lens specific reasoning observed	Cross lens tension summarised
Exercise 1: Forever product, a 100 year car, durability, value retention	<p>Technical: Defined durability criteria, system boundaries and decades scale serviceability, including parts replacement and compatibility over time.</p> <p>Economic: Identified revenue challenges under long lifetimes and long horizon obligations, including after sales support, liability and regulatory risk.</p> <p>Psychosocial: Raised trust and adoption limits, including preference change and perceived obsolescence even when functional quality is maintained.</p>	A durable design can be technically feasible, but a Circular Economy value retention strategy can fail if economic viability of long term support is weak or if user acceptance and trust are low.
Exercise 2: Design for R (Repair and reuse, Remanufacture, Recycle) on a smartphone, groups by value retention route	<p>Repair and reuse</p> <p>Technical: Prioritised modular design for fast replacement of key components, including an exchangeable battery, a swappable display and a swappable processor, framed as rapid restoration of function and longer usable life.</p> <p>Economic: Business model framed a product oriented offer with limited service and treated spare parts as a lever for reducing virgin material demand. Informational value through repaired products and replacement parts and generating failure pattern information to guide redesign.</p> <p>Psychosocial: Highlighted low confidence and limited skills for repair and proposed tutorials and repair networks, while addressing novelty preference through buy back, refurbishment and resale pathways.</p> <p>Remanufacture</p> <p>Technical: Proposed component modularity to enable refurbishment and upgrades, including exchangeable chips, a durable display and swappable and upgradable batteries.</p> <p>Economic: Business model framed a service oriented contract with planned return and replacement over multiple years. Environment value linked to reduced material purchasing and informational value based on insights on use and failure from returned products.</p> <p>Psychosocial: Preference for the newest smartphone and balance between new and remanufactured phone as the barriers. Messaging on environmental advantages.</p>	Value retention routes required different design choices and business logic across the three lenses, yet recurring adoption barriers persisted across routes, especially novelty preference, trust in repair or remanufacture and acceptance of feature and cost trade offs, indicating that route selection shifts which lens constraints dominate rather than removing cross lens competition.

Recycle

Technical: Prioritised design for separation and processing, including a single polymer choice, robotic disassembly and standardised batteries to reduce contamination and improve removal.

Economic: Business model framed as value capture through producer controlled take back and material recovery, for example deposit return or trade in credit, enabling predictable returns and revenue linked to recovered materials. Recycled content as a sourcing value and informational value through returned/collected products.

Psychosocial: Anticipated reduced features and higher costs as barriers and proposed marketing environmental benefits and seeking subsidies to offset cost implications.

Exercise 3: Biological loop, food waste problem across farm to fork

Technical: Proposed interventions across stages, including forecasting, shelf life support, logistics optimisation, dynamic pricing and household support tools.

Economic: Proposed incentive redesign and coordination, including local sourcing, donation pathways and waste charging linked to quantities.

Psychosocial: Proposed behavioural, cultural and legitimacy oriented measures, including information campaigns, retailer rules and carrot and stick instruments.

Food waste reduction is not a single point optimisation problem, because technical options require economic incentives and psychosocial legitimacy across multiple stages and stakeholders.

Group outputs refer to team summaries and completed group worksheets. Instructor notes refer to contemporaneous notes recorded during and immediately after plenary synthesis.

4.2 Shifts in reasoning demands across the exercise sequence

Across the three in class exercises, later tasks required higher integration demands, which is visible in the structure of the analysed outputs. This section reports shifts in task demands and in the reasoning that was made explicit, rather than changes in individual competence. First, the sequence moved from lens constrained reasoning to cross lens justification. Exercise 1 separated reasoning by assigning one lens per team, while Exercise 2 required each route group to combine technical changes, business model logic and psychosocial adoption conditions within a single justification. Second, the sequence moved from product level redesign to system and stakeholder reasoning. Exercise 2 centred on a single product and a defined value retention route, whereas Exercise 3 required stage specific proposals across farm to fork with an explicit responsible stakeholder, shifting reasoning toward coordination and actor alignment. Third, plenary synthesis increasingly required explicit naming of constraints and trade-offs. Later sessions required groups to state what enables proposed actions and what they displace, aligning with the course objective of justified Circular Economy decisions under irreducible tensions.

5. Discussion

5.1 Contribution to circular economy education

This paper contributes a transferable teaching architecture that operationalises circular economy competence as justified decision making under trade-offs rather than as recall of concepts or use of a single analytical tool. The Three-Lens Circular Economy Teaching Architecture makes the integration requirement explicit by requiring students to test whether a proposed circular strategy remains feasible, viable and acceptable when technology, economy and psychosocial constraints are considered together. The contribution is not the statement that circular economy spans multiple domains, but a repeatable decision scaffold that specifies the lenses, standardises guiding questions and uses structured activities to make reasoning visible at group level.

A common approach in higher education is to add circular economy content to existing engineering or business teaching while leaving integration to emerge implicitly through discussion or assessment (Sabri, 2025). This can result in students accumulating separate toolkits without a shared structure for reconciling conflicting conclusions across domains (Pargmann and Berding, 2025). The present approach addresses this gap by making integration a taught object through consistent prompts and forced comparison. The architecture also differs from widely used pedagogies such as problem-based learning, project-based learning and case-based teaching, which can leave technical, economic and social considerations juxtaposed rather than integrated through explicit justification (Allchin, 2013; Garcia-Saravia Ortiz-de-Montellano et al., 2023). In contrast, the present course design treats integration as a specific performance that must be scaffolded, practised and made visible through structured outputs and comparative synthesis. Compared with other circular economy education frameworks that present stepwise redesign pathways, the present architecture is positioned as an upstream decision scaffold rather than as a full redesign methodology (Garcia-Saravia Ortiz-de-Montellano et al., 2023). It supports first pass evaluation by foregrounding boundary setting, feasibility, incentives and adoption conditions before a specific redesign pathway is selected. This complements pathway focused approaches by clarifying which tensions must be resolved and which trade-offs are being accepted prior to detailed redesign work.

Published descriptions and reviews of Circular Economy courses in higher education commonly report active and experiential formats, including project based learning, challenge based learning and flipped classroom elements (Kirchherr and Piscicelli, 2019; González-Domínguez et al., 2020; Garcia-Saravia Ortiz-de-Montellano et al., 2023; Renfors, 2024). These approaches can be effective, evidence from educational psychology suggests they are not universally appropriate. Reviews of minimally guided instruction argue that, for novice learners in complex domains, discovery oriented designs can be less effective and less efficient than approaches that provide stronger guidance, because learners lack the prior knowledge structures needed to self direct learning without cognitive overload

(Kirschner et al., 2006). In line with this, cognitive load theory highlights the expertise reversal effect, indicating that the optimal level of guidance depends on learner expertise, with guidance particularly valuable at early stages and increasingly faded as internal guidance develops (Rey and Buchwald, 2011; Kalyuga and Sweller, 2018). This debate can be especially relevant for psychosocial aspects of Circular Economy decision making, where typical engineering background students often begin without shared concepts for cognitive biases, social acceptance, legitimacy and claim credibility. In such cases, a purely facilitative role can leave unspoken assumptions uncorrected. At the same time, problem based learning can succeed when it is scaffolded so that key strategies and disciplinary reasoning are made explicit rather than assumed (Hmelo-Silver et al., 2007). The course design in the present study responds to this conditionality by combining instructor led conceptual framing with repeated, structured application through the Three-Lens Architecture exercises, alongside extended peer and instructor contact through project clinics across the semester. This distributed format provides multiple opportunities for clarification and calibration, contrasting with short intensive blocks where misconceptions can persist with limited time for iterative feedback. Comparative studies of compressed and semester length teaching formats often report similar, and sometimes improved, performance outcomes, indicating that block delivery is not inherently inferior (Logan and Geltner, 2000; Carman and Bartsch, 2017). However, these comparisons rarely measure feedback cycles or whether students can act on feedback over time. Higher education feedback research emphasises that feedback is most effective when it functions as a loop, with timely input and subsequent opportunities for uptake and improvement, rather than as a one off message (Vlach and Sandhofer, 2012; Carless, 2019; Carpenter, 2020; Williams, 2024). This supports the rationale for a semester distributed structure when the goal is repeated clarification and recalibration, especially for psychosocial concepts. Evidence on flipped classroom designs also points to variability across contexts, supporting the choice to treat nontraditional formats as design options that require careful scaffolding rather than default solutions (Gillette et al., 2018; Strelan et al., 2020).

The exercise sequence in this study provides evidence that the architecture can elicit the kinds of contradictions and trade-offs that characterise circular economy decisions. Exercise 1 separated reasoning by assigning one lens per team, making conflicts visible when conclusions were compared. Exercise 2 required cross lens justification within one value retention route, linking design changes to business model logic and to adoption barriers on the same worksheet. Exercise 3 required stage specific reasoning across farm to fork with explicit stakeholder assignment, shifting the reasoning form toward coordination and actor alignment.

Plenary observations also suggest that the architecture makes common classroom difficulties pedagogically usable. Lens creep was observed during synthesis, meaning students sometimes introduced ideas from another lens while speaking from an assigned lens. This is interpretable as a predictable feature of early integration. The architecture provides a language for correction by asking students to label the lens of a claim before evaluating it.

5.2 Transferability and scope conditions

The architecture is designed for transfer because it separates stable components from context specific components. Stable components include the three lenses, the guiding question sets and the design principle of repeated application to the same problem followed by structured lens comparison in plenary. Context specific components include the chosen cases, the datasets used for micro interventions and the product or system selected for exercises. Transfer requires keeping the lens questions and the plenary comparison intact, since these elements make integration a visible performance rather than an implicit expectation.

Several scope conditions help readers judge fit. The course cohort was drawn mainly from informatics and engineering related bachelor programmes, so technical reasoning was expected to be familiar while psycho social reasoning was generally novel. The course is reported as a designed fourteen week sequence, while delivery in this implementation spanned ten to eleven teaching weeks due to scheduling, and the intended sequence is reported to support transfer. The analysed evidence was generated at group level, which fits seminar based teaching where discussion and synthesis are

central, but limits what can be claimed about individual development. The approach also assumes an active instructor role during plenary synthesis, including rapid lens labelling and guided comparison of conflicting conclusions, and transfer therefore depends on instructor willingness and ability to facilitate structured discussion. Class size is a practical constraint because the approach relies on instructor circulation during small group work and plenary synthesis that gives space for comparison across groups.

For practical adoption, three implementation recommendations follow from the course design. First, the lens language should be introduced early and used consistently so that claims can be labelled rapidly during plenary synthesis. Second, sequencing should begin with lens separation and move toward integration after students have learned the question sets, since immediate integration can overload novices. Third, time should be reserved for comparison and synthesis because decision competence becomes visible mainly when conclusions collide and groups must produce a defensible compromise under stated constraints.

5.3 Limitations

Analysed artefacts were generated at group level and interpreted alongside plenary notes. This supports a methods and pedagogy paper that illustrates what forms of reasoning can be elicited by the Three Lens Architecture, but it does not support strong claims about individual learning gains, retention or causal effects of specific sessions.

Instructor recorded notes introduce interpretation, particularly for Exercise 1 where the instructor selected what to capture as unique points, lens creep and synthesis outcomes. This limitation could be reduced in future studies through audio assisted capture, a structured observation template aligned to lens labels or a second observer. Lens creep also complicates strict classification of statements by lens and could be reduced by prompts that require explicit lens labelling before evaluation and by a short post discussion check in which groups identify where they crossed lenses.

Paraphrased student reflections also indicate refinement needs e.g. one reflection requested deeper treatment of psychosocial adoption and judgement while another raised concern that businesses may struggle to align fully with Circular Economy principles under current market conditions. These reflections point to extending psychosocial lens resources, clarifying how compromise decisions are justified and making space for discussion of feasibility constraints without implying that Circular Economy is unattainable.

6. Conclusion

This paper presented a Circular Economy teaching methodology developed and delivered at TH Köln that operationalises an integration requirement across technology, economy and psychosocial acceptance through a Three Lens Circular Economy Teaching Architecture. The analysed group artefacts and instructor notes from three embedded exercises show that the architecture makes lens specific reasoning visible and comparable and surfaces recurring cross lens tensions where technical feasibility, economic viability and acceptance constraints collide. The contribution is a transferable teaching scaffold that specifies lens questions and integration prompts, supporting evaluation of group level justifications under stated boundaries, assumptions and uncertainties, while remaining within the limits of qualitative group level evidence and without claiming individual learning gains or causal effects of specific sessions.

Data availability - The study reports group level course artefacts generated during three in class exercises. Worksheet templates are provided as Supplementary Material. No personal data were collected and the individual level datasets are confidential.

Author's contributions (CRediT taxonomy) - Himanshu Himanshu: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualisation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing; Christian Wolf: Funding acquisition, Writing – review and editing.

Funding - This contribution was funded by the project P_{LAN}_CV (reference number 03FHP109) which is funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) and Joint Science Conference (GWK).

Acknowledgements - The author thanks the students who participated in the course activities and contributed group level artefacts used in this study.

Conflict of interest - The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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